

MEETING ABSTRACTS

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P001

Effect of prolonged emergency department length of stay on process of care measures of critically ill patients

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Introduction: Prolonged boarding of critically ill patients in the emergency department (ED) may be associated with worse clinical outcomes. However, whether this association would exist in settings that have implemented a critical care consultation model in the ED remains unknown. We thus sought to explore the association between prolonged ED length of stay (LOS) and the deployment of evidence-based processes of care measures for critically ill patients in hospitals implementing a critical care consultation model in the ED.

Methods: We conducted a retrospective cohort study including eight academic intensive care units (ICUs) in Toronto, Ontario, Canada (i.e., Toronto Intensive Care Observational Registry: iCORE) from June 2014 to February 2023. We included adult patients who were directly admitted to the ICU from the ED. Patients with ED LOS for more than 24 h were excluded. The cohort was divided into an acceptable ED LOS group (LOS < 6 h) and a long ED LOS group (LOS 6–24 h). We explored the association between long ED LOS and processes of care measures on day 2 after admission to the ICU using logistic regression. Multivariable models were adjusted for age, sex, comorbidities, severity, study site, and diagnosis.

Results: We included 7072 patients, of whom 1462 (20.7%) patients had long ED LOS. Both groups had comparable severity at baseline. In the long ED LOS group, more patients had cardiovascular, chronic respiratory, and chronic kidney disease as comorbidities and fewer patients were admitted due to trauma. There was no difference in the deployment of processes of care measures on day 2 after admission to the ICU between the two groups, as shown in the Table.

Conclusions: In this multicenter study of ICUs in Toronto where a critical care consultation model has been implemented in the ED, long ED LOS was not associated with a decrease in the deployment of evidence-based processes of care measures for critically ill adult patients.

Table (abstract P001) Process of care measures on day 2

Process outcomes	Long ED LOS; N = 1462	Acceptable ED LOS; N = 5610	Adjusted odds ratio (95% CI)
Low tidal volume ventilation	174/281 (61.9%)	643/979 (65.7%)	0.84 (0.62–1.13)
Spontaneous breathing trial among those eligible	245/575 (42.6%)	950/2493 (38.1%)	1.09 (0.90–1.33)
Extubation among those eligible	116/179 (64.8%)	480/685 (70.1%)	0.76 (0.52–1.11)
DVT prophylaxis among those eligible	751/968 (77.6%)	2353/3225 (73%)	1.15 (0.96–1.37)
Continuous sedation	723/1186 (61%)	3002/4609 (65.1%)	0.92 (0.80–1.06)
Physical restraints	503/1184 (42.5%)	1979/4590 (43.1%)	1.08 (0.93–1.25)

P002

Development of intensive medicine in the emergency department: 1 year of experience in a tertiary referral hospital

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Introduction: The assimilation of Intensive Care Specialist (ICS) into the Emergency Department (ED) is a recent development in the southern part of the country supported by the recommendation of the Order of Physicians (OM) for the presence of intensivists in the

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exchange variables allowed for more precise patient stratification. These findings have the potential to optimize individualized treatment selection and improve clinical outcomes in ARDS patients.

References

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2. Matthay MA et al. Am J Respir Crit Care Med. 2024;209:37–47

Table (abstract P146) Characteristics of ARDS subphenotypes on the first day of ventilation for included patients

Variable	Subphenotype 1 (n = 172)	Subphenotype 2 (n = 52)	p value
Mechanical power (J/min)	17.21 (14.11–19.84)	21.61 (17.58–29.09)	< 0.001*
Tidal volume (mL/kg/PBW)	4.37 (4.02–4.82)	3.84 (2.96–4.59)	< 0.001*
Driving pressure (cmH ₂ O)	10 (8–11)	11 (10–12)	< 0.001*
Total respiratory rate (rpm)	24 (20–26)	30 (26–36)	< 0.001*
VD/VT	0.5 (0.43–0.57)	0.62 (0.54–0.73)	< 0.001*
EtCO ₂ (mmHg)	30.5 (33–35.5)	36 (34–41)	< 0.001*
28-Day Mortality	16 (9.3%)	11 (21.15%)	0.021*

Statistical significance was assessed using the Mann-Whitney test, with a significance level set at *p* < 0.05. Values are expressed as median (interquartile range). Qualitative variables are presented as absolute frequency (relative frequency). VD/VT (dead space volume/tidal volume), EtCO₂ (end-tidal CO₂)

P147

Exploration of COVID-19 associated bradycardia using heart rate variability analysis in a case-control study of ARDS patients

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Introduction: The bradycardia and dysautonomia observed during SARS-Cov2 infection have raised questions about the involvement of the autonomic nervous system (ANS). Data on ANS dysregulation and its association with outcomes are limited. We aimed to investigate sympathovagal balance, assessed by heart rate variability (HRV), and its clinical prognostic value in patients with acute respiratory distress syndrome (ARDS) related to COVID-19 (C-ARDS) or to other aetiologies (NC-ARDS).

Methods: A single-centre prospective case-control study was conducted. Consecutive patients fulfilling ARDS criteria between 2020 and 2022 were included. HRV was assessed offline from 1-h electrographic tracings using time and frequency measures and compared between C-ARDS and NC-ARDS.

Results: During the study period, 24 C-ARDS and 19 NC-ARDS were included. Median heart rate was significantly lower in C-ARDS than in NC-ARDS (60 [53–72] versus 101 [91–112] bpm, *p* < 0.001). HRV was

significantly impaired in both C-ARDS and NC-ARDS patients (Table). Almost all time and frequency parameters of HRV were significantly less impaired in C-ARDS patients than in NC-ARDS patients. HRV correlated with heart rate only in C-ARDS patients. No significant differences in HRV parameters were found when comparing survivors and non-survivors. A positive correlation was found between low to high frequency ratio (LF/HF) and ICU length of stay (*r* = 0.576, *p* < 0.001). Other HRV variables were not correlated with clinical outcomes.

Conclusions: This prospective study confirms that C-ARDS is associated with marked bradycardia and severe ANS impairment. HRV was less severely impaired and correlated with heart rate only in COVID-19 patients, suggesting a sympathovagal imbalance with vagal overtone. Our study did not find a robust predictive value of HRV analysis, but poor outcomes seemed more related to sympathetic than parasympathetic hyperactivation.

Table (abstract P147) Heart rate variability parameters

Heart Rate Variability	All ARDS (n = 43)	C-ARDS (n = 24)	NC-ARDS (n = 19)	p value
Heart rate (bpm)	77 [57–100]	60 [53–72]	101 [91–112]	< 0.001
RR interval (ms)	778 [600–1046]	1004 [836–1142]	595 [538–661]	< 0.001
SDRR (ms)	15 [9–36]	25 [14–46]	10 [7–18]	0.002
VLF (ms)	60 [17–164]	108 [67–257]	19 [3.9–42]	< 0.001
LF (ms)	10 [3.0–29]	15 [10–69]	3.0 [0.71–9.0]	< 0.001
HF (ms)	22 [7.7–64]	31 [18–128]	9.1 [4.0–27]	< 0.001
LF/HF ratio	0.36 [0.13–0.71]	0.45 [0.32–0.87]	0.18 [0.09–0.44]	0.018

Data are presented as medians and interquartile range. ARDS: acute respiratory distress syndrome; C-ARDS: Covid-19 related ARDS; NC-ARDS: non-Covid-19 related ARDS; SDRR: standard deviation of RR intervals; VLF: very low-frequency; LF: low-frequency; HF: high-frequency; bpm: beats per minute.

P148

Biomarkers of alveolocapillary membrane injury in COVID-19 related ARDS: a pilot study

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Introduction: We aimed to investigate serum biomarkers of alveolocapillary membrane injury (sRAGE, endocan and angiopoietin-2) in COVID-19 related ARDS as prognostic markers of 28 day mortality.

Methods: An observational, retrospective pilot study was conducted on mechanically ventilated patients, admitted to Institute for pulmonary diseases of Vojvodina from December 2020 until June 2021. All patients fulfilled Berlin criteria for ARDS while SARS CoV-2 infection was proven positive by RT-PCR of nasopharyngeal swab. Within 48 h from starting mechanical ventilation the blood samples were taken for measurement of serum biomarkers (sRAGE, endocan, angiopoietin-2). We collected baseline demographic data, Charlson comorbidity index, APACHE II, SOFA and SAPS2 score, procalcitonin and CRP values, neutrophil/lymphocyte ratio, PaO₂/FIO₂ ratio, PEEP and driving pressure values, presence of septic shock at admission and need for VV-ECMO support. The primary endpoint was 28-day mortality.

Results: A total of 36 patients were included in the study (Table). The average age was 65 (IQR 16), the observed group consisted of 11 (30.6%) females. Arterial hypertension and obesity were the most common comorbidities. Median Charlson score was 2.5 ± 2 , median APACHE II score 20 (IQR 9), median SOFA score 5 (IQR 3) and median SAPS2 score 3 (IQR 16). Overall mortality was 63.9%. Septic shock was present in 25 (69.4%) patients and 3 patients needed VV-ECMO support. There were no differences observed in the level of measured biomarkers with respect to 28 days mortality for endocan and angiotensin-2 (1.65 ng/mL, IQR 2.7 ng/mL vs. 2.53, IQR 3.47 ng/mL, $p=0.21$ and 1.15 ng/mL, IQR 3.39 ng/mL vs. 2.15, IQR 3.17 ng/mL, $p=0.24$) respectively. Level of sRAGE was lower in COVID survivors but difference did not reach statistical significance (5263 pg/mL, IQR 18,601 pg/mL vs. 18,750, IQR 23,744 pg/mL, $p=0.1$).

Conclusions: Serum value of sRAGE may serve as promising biomarker for COVID-19 ARDS prognostication and clinical trial enrichment, but further studies are needed.

Table (abstract P148) Laboratory findings and parameters of mechanical ventilation

	COVID-19 survivors at day 28, n = 13	COVID-19 non-survivors at day 28, n = 23
C-reactive protein (mg/mL) median, IQR	157 (141.1)	113.5 (108.5)
Procalcitonin (ng/mL) median, IQR	0.22 (0.7)	0.35 (1.18)
Neutrophil/lymphocyte ratio median, IQR	13 (18.6)	15.8 (17.1)
PaO ₂ /FIO ₂ median, IQR	77 (104)	83 (38)
PEEP median, IQR	10 (4)	12 (2)
Driving pressure median, IQR	13 (6)	12 (5)

P149

Compliance of the respiratory system in patients with COVID-19 and non-COVID-19 ARDS

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Introduction: The comparison of respiratory system compliance (Crs) between COVID19 (Coronavirus disease 2019) non-COVID19 ARDS (acute respiratory distress syndrome) patients has been the object of debate, but few studies have evaluated it when considering applied positive end expiratory pressure (PEEP), which is one of the known determinants of Crs itself. The aim of this study was to compare Crs taking into account the applied PEEP [1].

Methods: Two cohorts of patients were created: those with COVID-ARDS and those with non-COVID ARDS. In the whole sample the association between Crs and type of ARDS at different PEEP levels was adjusted for anthropometric and clinical variables. As secondary analyses, patients were matched for predicted functional residual capacity and the same association was assessed. Moreover, the association between Crs and type of ARDS was reassessed at predefined PEEP level of 0, 5, 8, 12, and 15 cmH₂O with a propensity score-weighted linear model.

Results: 263 patients were included in the study, 159 patients with COVID-ARDS and 104 with non-COVID ARDS. The association between Crs and type of ARDS was not significant in both the complete cohorts ($p=0.11$) and in the matched cohorts ($p=0.96$). This was true also for the propensity score weighted association at PEEP 5, 8, 12 and 15 cmH₂O, while it was statistically significant at PEEP 0 (with a median difference of 2 mL/cmH₂O, which is not clinically significant).

Conclusions: The compliance of the respiratory system is similar between COVID ARDS and non-COVID ARDS when calculated at the same PEEP level and while taking into account patients' anthropometric characteristics.

Reference

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P150

Analysis of ventilation-perfusion mismatch by electrical impedance tomography and the severity of experimental lung injury

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Introduction: The exclusion of one lung from ventilation or perfusion alters the distribution of tidal volume and pulmonary blood flow with impairment of V/Q matching and development of pathological mechanisms inducing lung injury. The measure of V/Q mismatch by Electrical Impedance Tomography (EIT) is regional and could be more accurate than classic global measures of intrapulmonary shunt and physiological dead space (DS).

Methods: Sedated and paralyzed pigs were mechanically ventilated (Vt 15 mL/Kg, PEEP 1 cmH₂O, RR 15, FIO₂ 0.5) for 24 h: 11 underwent ligation (non-perfused lung injury, NPLI) and 10 exclusion (non-ventilated lung injury, NVLI) of the left lung (LL). Physiological and EIT data were collected along the experiment, and histological score (HS) after sacrifice.

Results: In the LL, EIT data showed that nearly all the ventilation was distributed to the DS and high V/Q compartments (Figure panels A and B) in the NPLI group, while the LL of the NVLI group was characterized by 100% of ventilation reaching the shunt compartment (Figure panel C). In the right lung (RL) of the NVLI group, most of ventilation reached the DS and high V/Q compartments (Figure panels D and E), and around 80% of perfusion reached high V/Q units (Figure panel F). In the RL of the NPLI group, instead, large fraction of ventilation and perfusion reached the normal V/Q compartment (Figure panels G and H). Physiological DS differed only after 2 h from start and then was similar between the two groups (Figure panel I). The calculated shunt fraction was low (less than 20%) in both groups and only slightly higher in the NVLI group (Figure panel J). Higher degree of V/Q mismatch in both lungs of the NVLI group was associated with more severe HS compared to the NPLI group (LL HS: NVLI 10.3 ± 2.0 vs. NPLI 6.4 ± 1.6 , $p < 0.0001$; RL HS: NVLI 5.5 ± 2.0 vs. NPLI 3.0 ± 0.7 , $p < 0.001$).

Conclusions: Analysis of V/Q mismatch by EIT is more accurate than classic global measures and could be directly correlated with the severity of lung injury.